

Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the mapping of research topics around Savings Banks Country (BTN) Sharia And Conventional with approach mix-method, that is studies VOSviewer bibliometrics and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping number of distribution of journal publications regarding BTN; (2) mapping bibliometric visualization results VOSviewer around the BTN ratio based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics around the BTN ratio using a Library Research study. Research result show that: (1) based on mapping amount spread publication journal, there is 395 journal publications regarding the BTN ratio; (2) based on VOSviewer bibliometric study mapping, network visualization results around the BTN ratio divided into 15 clusters and 97 topic items; (3) based on mapping studies Library Researchs, there is 9 theme main around BTN. Difference study This with study previously is on study This explain And map all over topic study around BTN, so that researcher Next, you can find out the gaps in research regarding BTN. Implications and contributions study This is exists mapping topics study around BTN Which often or seldom researched by researcher, so that can become reference for researcher furthermore.

Keywords: Bank Tabungan Negara; BTN Syariah; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research

Introduction

Bank Savings Country (BTN) has experience development Which significant for years. This bank continues to develop its branch network throughout Indonesia And offer various product And service banking to public (Kasmidar, 2021). Besides That, BTN Also role in manage program government For increasing access to housing for the community, such as Home Ownership Credit (KPR) subsidy. Over the last few years, BTN has also been active in developing services digital banking to increase ease of access for customers. Via app mobile banking And Internet banking, customers can do transaction banking, check balances, pay bills, and perform other banking activities with easy (Iswanaji, 2021). However, to obtain the latest information about developments latest BTN, recommended For visit site web official BTN or contact the bank directly for get information Which accurate And latest (Lubis, 2022).

Whereas BTN Sharia established on year 2009 And has focused on development of products and services in accordance with sharia principles. Since that, bank This keep experiencing development (Maulida, 2021). Several things Which Possible become factor important in development Bank BTN Sharia in Indonesia is: First, BTN Syariah has actively developed a network of branch offices in various regions in Indonesia. With own more Lots branch, they can give service Which more easy accessed for its customers (Sembiring, 2021). Second, BTN Sharia Keep going develop products and services in accordance with sharia principles. This includes financing housing area sharia, financing vehicle sharia, as well as product savings And sharia deposits (Apriono, 2020). Third, BTN Syariah can establish partnerships with other financial institutions to expand services and reach more target markets wide. This kind of collaboration can help increase accessibility and penetration BTN Syariah market (Muslikh, 2020).

Study previous about BTN Sharia And Conventional can done with various

approaches and different research focuses. Here are some topics which can become a base study about second type bank. This study is divided into three parts. First, a study which compares the performance of finance in BTN Sharia with Conventional in terms of profitability, liquidity, efficiency, asset quality and other relevant factors. In this case, research can analyze existing financial data, such as financial reports annual and report finance per quarter (Chusna, 2019). Study second, a study which reviews customer preferences regarding the choice between BTN Syariah and Conventional. This matter can be done through surveys or interviews with customers who have used it or own account in either one or second bank. Factors which can be considered include religious beliefs, financial benefits, products and services offered, and other factors that influence customer decisions (Debara, 2019). Study third, a study which compares product and service offered by BTN Syariah and Conventional. For example, research can evaluate savings products, housing loans, investments, or other products from both banks. The focus of the research may be a comparison of features, benefits, costs, and terms applied to these products and services (Hutajulu & Reza, 2018). Study fourth, research that looks at the influence of government regulations and policies on development of BTN Syariah and Conventional. Study this can involve analysis regarding applicable sharia banking and conventional banking policies, regulations government, incentives or fiscal incentives provided, and the influence of these factors to growth and development banks (Darmawan, 2018). Study fifth, a study which focuses on customer experience in interacting with BTN Sharia and Conventional. Method study which can be used is an in-depth interview, observation, or analysis of data from a bank's communication channels like service customer, media social, or platforms online. Study this can discuss customer satisfaction, service quality, communication effectiveness, and other aspects influence customer experience (Suciani et al., 2018).

Objective study This is for map topic study around Bank Savings Country (BTN) Sharia and Conventional in Indonesia by using: (1) studies VOSviewer bibliometrics to analyze and study literature development maps in publication something field science with make map network metadata; And (2) studies literature useful review analyze, identify and review _ articles from the journal Nationally accredited Sinta. The difference between this research and previous research is on study This explain And map all over topic study around BTN, so that researcher furthermore can know emptiness study around BTN. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics around BTN is often or rarely studied by researchers, so it can be a reference for researcher furthermore.

Literature Review

Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) is a government-owned bank in Indonesia which focus on financing sector housing area. BTN established on date 5 February 1897 with the name Postpaarbank which functions as a serving banking institution customers For keep Money in form savings (Sambouw et al., 2017). On beginning In its founding, BTN was under the supervision of De Javasche Bank, the central bank of the Indies Dutch moment That. Whereas Bank Savings Country (BTN) Sharia is part from BTN which operate based on principles sharia Islam (Ma'ruf, 2018). Bank This providing financial products and services that comply with sharia law. Principle The main thing implemented in its operations is the prohibition of usury (interest) and transactions involving usury. Bank BTN Syariah offers various banking products such as sharia housing financing, sharia savings, sharia deposits, and other products which in accordance with sharia principles (Wibisono & Purwanti, 2018).

Bibliometric studies involve quantitative analysis of scientific publications and literature using bibliographic data. VOSviewer is the software used in studies

bibliometrics. VOSviewer used For analyze network collaboration between author, institution, or research field based on bibliographic data collected from source like base data indexation scientific. VOSviewer provide features For visualize And analyze network collaboration between writer or institution based on co-authorship (collaborative joint writing), co-citation (joint writing in the reference list), or co-occurrence (co-occurrence in the same article) (Dubyna et al., 2022). By using analysis techniques such as cluster mapping And analysis text, VOSviewer help identify pattern collaboration Which There is, describe relationships between authors or institutions, and identify research trends which is relevant. In bibliometric analysis, VOSviewer can help researchers to understand structure collaboration in field certain, identify centers study significant ones, or explore research trends and emerging themes. VOSviewer can also be used to carry out visual analysis of scientific publications with mapping key words that frequently appear in literature or analyzing citations between articles scientific (van Eck NJ, 2022).

A Library Research study is a type of research carried out with the purpose of investigating, evaluating, and combining research findings that have previously existed in a particular field. In this study, researchers conducted review to literature Which relevant And choose studies Which related with topic Which currently researched. Objective from studies Library Research is For gain a comprehensive understanding of the topic under study, identify research gaps, and present existing findings in the literature. The method used in this study involves searching and selecting literature relevant, analysis critical to literature Which chosen, as well as preparation report Which explain the findings that have been found. A Library Research study can be carried out as study independent or as part from study Which more wide. Results from studies Library Research usually used For support argument, identify lack study previously, or give base for study more carry on in the same field. By conducting a Library Research study, researchers can obtain deep insight into the topic being researched, identifying research trends, understand the differences in existing approaches or findings, and prepare the basis for research Which solid. Studies This Also help in avoid duplication study Which No need And direct study to direction Which more directed And meaningful (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. Object his research is Bank Savings Country (BTN). Type data Which used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Bank State Savings (BTN) Sharia and Conventional.

Source taking data originate from search journal national accredited Sintavia the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) and Perish/Harzing software. Analysis tools data using Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer software. Technique collection data includes: (1) open software Perish/Harzing, Then look for journal based on the title words category, the key words are " Bank Tabungan Negara " and "BTN" in the whole year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify title journal Which double; (3) download files format RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) from all journals that have been collected the data; and (4) inserting files data RIS inward Mendeley software Desktop.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around BTN use Microsoft Excel And Mendeley Desktop based on year publishing; mapping bibliometric network visualization results and journal publication trends around BTN use software algorithm VOSviewer (Visualization of

Similarities) based on number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping research topics surrounding BTN use studies Library Research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Spread Publication Journal around Bank Savings Country (BTN) Sharia And Conventional

There are 395 national journals accredited by Sinta based on data collection results using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop which comes from the Garuda website (Garba Reference Digital) And software Perish/Harzing during period 2003 until year 2023. The result is as following:

Table 1. Journal publication data regarding BTN Syariah and Conventional based on year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2003	1	2014	26	2019	32
2007	1	2015	30	2020	36
2011	1	2016	46	2021	43
2012	6	2017	32	2022	62
2013	19	2018	44	2023	16

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Mapping Topic Study around Bank Savings Country (BTN) Sharia And Conventional use Studies Bibliometrics

Article search results in the Perish/Harzing software are exported in format RIS (Research Information Systems), then input and analyzed using device soft VOSviewer. The result is as following:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding BTN Syariah And Conventional.

Source: Data processed, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

VOSViewer software visualization results related to research development maps around BTN Sharia And Conventional there is 15 cluster And 97 items topic on mapping the, including the following: Cluster 1 consists of 13 topic items, namely: assets, bank btn, bni, Padang branch, car, data, in Indonesia, Indonesia, bank health, method, management, return, time. Cluster 2 consists from 9 items topic, that is: bank savings country sharia palembang, BTN Syariah, Pekanbaru branch, FLPP, KCP Parepare, home ownership credit, products, studies. Cluster 3 consists of 9 topic items, namely: Surakarta branch, work discipline, bank employees state savings, motivation, state savings banks, work stress, branch office sharia surakarta, sharia Semarang. Cluster 4 consists from 9 items topic, that is: apht, btn ib, btn ib house, BTN KCS Malang, Customer, Financing, Surakarta Syariah Branch Office, Realization, Syariah poor branch. Cluster 5 consists of 8 topic items, namely: Banda Aceh, branch office, case, determinant, employees, office branch Medan, office branch Pekanbaru, population. Cluster 6 consists of 8 topic items, namely: Yogyakarta branch, Banjarmasin sharia branch office, October, student work practice program, product marketing strategy, Surabaya, savings btn. Cluster 7 consists of 6 topic items, namely: bank btn syariah makassar, branch, party fund, Qardh at PT, Sharia Savings Bank, Makassar Branch Sharia. Cluster 8 consists of 6 items topics, namely: state savings bank, bcfu, implementation, jakarta, sharia branch office Surakarta, KPR BTN IB Financing. Cluster 9 consists of 6 topic items, namely: bank btn tbk, pt bank savings country, semarang, sharia Pekanbaru, to performance, units business sharia. Cluster 10 consists of 4 topic items, namely: bank btn syariah banjarmasin, sharia branch, tbk branch sharia. Cluster 11 consists of 4 topic items, namely: BTN Platinum at PT, Solo branch office, company, tbk office branch sharia. Cluster 12 consists from 4 items topic, that is: brawijaya branch office, demand, mortgage loan, Pekanbaru. Cluster 13 consists of 4 topic items, namely: office sub-branch, KCPS, bank, service. Cluster 14 consists of 4 topic items, namely: contracts murabahah on bank savings country, in bank savings country, sharia branch Yogyakarta. Cluster 15 consists of 3 topic items, namely: IBS repository, Cibubur branch office, ojk.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Performance Sharia and Conventional State Savings Bank (BTN) finances

Library Research study in previous research journals, researcher find 22 factor Which influence performance finance/profitability BTN Sharia and Conventional, that is:

(1) Burden Operational to Income Operational/BOPO; (2) BI-7 Day Reverse Repo Rate/BI-7DRR; (3) Allowance for Impairment Losses/CKPN; (4) Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR; (5) Capital Assets Earnings; (6) Capital Budgeting Analysis; (7) Covid-19; (8) Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR; (9) Third Party Funds/DPK; (10) Good Corporate Governance/GCG; (11) Price share; (12) Internal auditing; (13) Loans to Deposits Ratio/LDR; (14) Liquidity; (15) Capital Work; (16) Net Profit Margin/NPM; (17) Net Interest Margin/NIM; (18) Non Performing Loans/NPL; (19) Planning profit; (20) Profile risk; (21) Ratio liquidity, solvency, profitability; And (22) Economic recession.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Performance Sharia and Conventional State Savings Bank (BTN) employees

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 47 factors that influence the performance of BTN Syariah employees and Conventional,

that is:

(1) Assessment center at BTN KC Malang; (2) Work load at BTN KC Manado; (3) Organizational culture at BTN KC Manado, Medan, Semarang, Pekanbaru, Bandung, Gresik, Palembang, Jember, Solo, Makassar, Banjarmasin; (4) Work discipline at BTN KC Batam, Denpasar, Manado, Palembang, Surakarta; (5) Management diversity at BTN KC Solo; (6) Self-efficacy at BTN KC Solo; (7) Work facilities at BTN KC Medan; (8) Salary at BTN KC Solo, Medan, Manado; (9) Work relations at BTN KC Pekanbaru, Bandung; (10) Characteristics work in BTN KC Medan; (11) Intelligence emotional in BTN KC Surakarta, Bengkulu; (12) Intellectual intelligence at BTN KC Bengkulu; (13) Spiritual intelligence at BTN KC Bengkulu; (14) Ability to work at BTN KC Surabaya, Makassar; (15) Leadership transformational in BTN KC Manado, Semarang, Denpasar, Pekanbaru, Surakarta, Poor; (16) Work The same team in BTN KC Medan; (17) Consistency education in BTNS KC Poor; (18) Social competency at BTN KC Bandung, Manado, Solo, Palu; (19) Compensation at BTN KC Semarang, Manado, Palembang, Surakarta, Bangkalan; (20) Interpersonal communication in BTN KC Medan, Semarang, Surakarta, Malang, Banjarmasin; (21) Organizational commitment in BTN KC Pekanbaru, Gresik; (22) Satisfaction Work (BTN KC Bekasi, Medan, BTNS Pekanbaru; (23) Working environment/climate at BTN KC Semarang, Malang, Medan, Pontianak, Manado, Kediri, Padang; (24) Work motivation at BTN KC Semarang, Manado, Surabaya, Denpasar, Palembang, Pekanbaru, Pontianak, Surakarta, Kediri, Makassar, Medan; (25) Optimism in BTN KC Solo; (26) Job training at BTN KC Manado, Padang; (27) Job placement in BTN KC Surabaya, Manado, Palembang, Kediri; (28) Supervision in BTN KC Palembang; (29) Performance management in BTN KC Poor; (30) Development career in BTN KC Solo, Medan, Pekanbaru, Manado, Kediri, BTNS KC Semarang; (31) Leadership behavior at BTN KC Manado; (32) Education at BTN KC Manado; (33) Personality at BTN KC Jember; (34) Experience Work in BTN KC Solo; (35) Political skills in BTN KC Surabaya; (36) Professionalism in BTN KC Poor; (37) Colleague Work in BTN KC Solo; (38) Recruitment in BTN KC Palu; (39) Work enthusiasm at BTN KC Batam; (40) Work stress at BTN KC Manado, Surakarta, Bekasi, Batam, Medan; (41) Supervisor at BTN KC Solo; (42) Teamwork at BTN KC Surakarta; (43) Training Evaluation Process using KIRKPATRICK'S Training Evaluation Model at BTN; (44) Turnover Intention at BTN KC Bekasi; (45) Employment benefits in BTN KC Kediri; (46) Work balance at BTNS KC Semarang; and (47) Workload at BTNS KC Pekanbaru.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Loyalty Customers make transactions at Sharia and Conventional State Savings Banks (BTN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 40 factors that influence customer loyalty when transacting at BTN Sharia and Conventional, that is:

(1) Product attributes at BTN KC Cikarang, Probolinggo; (2) Brand image at BTN KC Semarang; (3) Image company in BTN KC Madiun, Manado, Semarang; (4) Customers value at BTN KC Medan; (5) Digital banking at BTNS; (6) Islamic business ethics at BTNS KC Bogor; (7) Islamic work ethic at BTNS KC Malang; (8) E-Banking at BTN KC Slamet Riyadi Solo; (9) Experiential marketing at BTN KCU Brawijaya Malang; (10) Prices at BTNS KC Malang; (11) Connection customers in BTN KC Cicaheum, Padang; (12) Policy intensive roleplay customers service at BTN KC Bogor; (13) Trust in BTN KC Madiun; (14) Satisfaction at BTN KC Madiun, Balikpapan, Manado; (15) Confidentiality/security data in BTN KC Jakarta Center; (16) Employee competency frontliners in BTN KC Palembang, Cibubur; (17) Communication marketing at BTN KC Bekasi, BTNS KC Banda Aceh; (18) Commitment to BTNS KC Malang, Madiun; (19) Quality service in BTN KC

Cikarang, Gresik, Samarinda, Balikpapan, Manado, Malang, Bandar Lampung, Medan, Madiun, Solo, Semarang, Cibubur, Karawang, BTNS KC Bogor, Solo; (20) Quality product in BTN KC Coconut Ivory, Karawang; (21) Quality network Internet in BTN; (22) Literacy finance in BTNS KC Medan; (23) M-Banking in BTNS KC Solo; (24) Islamic values at BTN KC Semarang, BTNS KC Solo; (25) Priority customer behavior in BTN KC Malang; (26) Notification of interest rate increases at BTN KC Pontianak; (27) Knowledge at BTNS KC Malang; (28) Customer Service at BTN KC Bogor, UNESA, Tangerang, KCP Cibinong; (29) Security services at BTN KC Tangerang; (30) Service Tellers in BTN KC Tangerang; (31) Personal selling in BTN; (32) Physical evidence at BTN KC Semarang; (33) Portfolio services at BTN KC Semarang; (34) Promotion at BTN KC Bogor, Cikarang, Probolinggo, Kelapa Gading, BTNS KC Malang; (35) Servqual at BTN KC Madiun; (36) Strategy marketing in BTN KCP Kopo; (37) Strategy product in BTNS KC Poor; (38) Strategy experiential marketing in BTN KC Semarang; (39) Savings Taplus young in BTN KC Pondok Pinang; and (40) Total Quality Management/TQM at BTN KC UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Sharia and State Savings Bank (BTN) Products Conventional

Library Research study in previous research journals, researcher found 14 product BTN Syariah And Conventional, that is: (1) Capital credit at BTN KC Samarinda; (2) Home/KAR Collateral Credit at BTN KC Manado; (3) Murabahah financing at BTNS KC Parepare, Malang, Makassar, Batam; (4) Financing Mudharabah in BTNS KC Makassar, Semarang; (5) Financing Musharakah in BTNS KC Pekanbaru; (6) Construction financing at BTNS KC Bogor; (7) Funding bailout Hajj contract Mudharabah Muthlaqah, Qard in BTNS KC Poor, Bogor, Makassar; (8) Financing multiservice with contract Kafalah bill Ujrah in BTNS KCPS Suropati Cores Bandung; Loan financing for pivot apartment ownership by pre-project selling at BTN KC Jakarta Center; (10) Product ATM up to in BTN KC Madiun; (11) Program a million House in BTN KCP Banyuwangi; (12) Mudharabah deposit savings at BTNS KC Pekanbaru; (13) Wadiah yad dhamanah savings at BTNS KC Palembang; and (14) Retirement savings in BTN Office Suryakencana Cash.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Home Ownership Credit/KPR Financing in Bank Savings Country (BTN) Sharia And Conventional

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 28 Home Ownership Credit/KPR financing at BTN Syariah and Conventional (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Goddess, 2023), that is:

(1) KPR Accounting at BTNS KC Surabaya; (2) Murabahah bil Wakalah contract in KPR at BTNS KC Bogor; (3) Analysis of the ability to pay KPR at BTNS KC Bogor; (4) Factors for taking a BTN KPR include: credit interest rates, service quality, Loan to Value, Non Performing Loan/NPL, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR at BTN KC Solo; (5) Legal relationship between banks and property companies at BTN; (6) Law on buying and selling mortgages in underhand at BTN KC Pontianak; (7) Auction with execution parate at BTN KC Solo; (8) Risk management in accordance with BI Circular No. 15/40/DKMP on KPR at BTN KC Kediri; (9) Management credit problem/jam in BTN KC Padang through forum non litigation, BTNS KC Malang, Pekanbaru, Bogor; (10) The role of notary/PPAK at BTN KC Manado, Pekanbaru; (11) KPR development using trend analysis at BTN KC Cimahi; (12) Products mortgage in BTN KCP Sawojajar Poor, KC Denpasar, Solo, Makassar, Bogor, Maros, Mataram, BTNS KC Bekasi, Surakarta; (13) Legal protection for KPR customers at BTN KC Manado, Malang, Sungguminasa Gowa, Palu, BTNS KC Bogor; (14) Internal control at BTNS KC Poor, BTN KC Balikpapan, Gresik; (15) Calculation flower credit mortgage in BTN KC Bogor; (16) Application ta'widh in accordance fatwa DSN-MUI No. 43 Year 2004 in BTN KC Jombang; (17) Application 5C in product mortgage in

BTN KC Banda Aceh; (18) Influence mortgage to Non Performing Loans/NPL, Return On Assets/ROA; (19) Restructuring KPR financing at BTN KC Banyuwangi; (20) Information system for decision making on granting KPR at BTN KC Poor; (21) KPR payment system at BTN KC Pontianak; (22) Realization prediction system New Commercial Mortgage at BTN KC Karawaci; (23) Internal control system at BTN Unit Lumbanjulu; (24) Subsidy mortgage in BTN KC Manado, Banjarbaru; (25) Take over debtor in KPR at BTN KC Samarinda, Pontianak; (26) Review of Islamic law in KPR products in BTNS KC Semarang, Cirebon; (27) Overview on segmentation, determination market target And positioning at BTN KCP Dramaga Bogor; (28) Debtor default in KPR at BTN KC Pontianak, Banda Aceh, BTNS KC Surabaya, Bogor.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Giving Credit at the Sharia and Conventional State Savings Bank (BTN)

Library Research study in previous research journals, researcher find 10 factors Which influence giving credit on BTN Sharia And Conventional (Rohmandika et al., 2023), that is:

(1) Internal audit at BTN KC Bengkulu; (2) Third Party Funds/DPK at BTN KC Tasikmalaya; (3) Five C'S of Credit Analysis at BTN KC Pamekasan; (4) Inflation at BTN; (5) Credit capital work/KMK in BTN KC Kediri; (6) Report finance in BTN KC Manado; (7) Mark exchange at BTN; (8) Per capita income at BTN; (9) Internal control system at BTN KC Ternate, Banda Aceh; And (10) Responsibility juridical in BTN KC Denpasar.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Customer Take Credit on Bank Savings Country (BTN) Sharia And Conventional

Library Research study in previous research journals, Researchers found 13 factors that influence customers to take credit BTN Sharia And Conventional (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Goddess, 2023), that is:

(1) Company image at BTN KC Gresik; (2) Management functions at BTN KC Muara Bungo; (3) Period stone credit in BTN KC Poor; (4) Awareness brand in BTN KC Semarang; (5) Quality service in BTN KC Gresik; (6) Loans to Value in BTN KC Poor; (7) Income in BTN KC Poor, Prabumulih; (8) Service in BTN KC Semarang; (9) Condition in BTN KC Jember; (10) Product Domestic Gross/GDP in BTN; (11) Promotion in BTN KC Gresik; (12) Ethnic group flower in BTN KC Semarang, Gresik, Jember, Iskandar Muda Medan, Prabumulih; And Subsidy installments in BTN KC Jember.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Performance Comparison of State Savings Banks (BTN) Sharia And Conventional with Bank Other

Library Research study in previous research journals, researcher find 4 comparison performance BTN Sharia And Conventional with bank other (Budianto & Goddess, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023), that is: (1) Financial performance between Bank Muamalat Indonesia and BTNS; (2) Implementation Good Corporate Governance/GCG between Bank Muamalat Indonesia And BTNS; (3) Application contract mortgage between Bank Muamalat Indonesia And BTNS; And (4) Difference priceshares, share trading volume, stock returns before and after plan information acquisition between BTN And Bank Independent.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Other Problems that

Occur in Banks State Savings (BTN) Sharia and Conventional

Library Research study in previous research journals, researcher find 43 problem other Which happen on BTN Sharia And Conventional (Budianto, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023), that is: (1) Accounting for problem/non-performing loans with the effectiveness of Cessie at BTN KC Malang, Pekanbaru, BTNS KC Indramayu; (2) Fair price of shares using the Discounted Cash method Flow in BTN; (3) Law giving facility credit with guarantee right dependents ranked at BTN KC Malang; (4) Credit collateral using a deposit pledge at BTN KC Solo; (5) Sell buy in lower hand happen congestion in BTN KC Lhokseumawe; (6) Accounting fraud at BTN KC Medan; (7) Disaster preparedness with suitability use of safety signs at BTN; (8) Bad credit at BTN KC Bengkulu; (9) Loan to Value at BTN KC Singaraja, Kediri; (10) Interest tax on savings withholding tax system at BTN KC Tomohon; (11) Murabahah financing was problematic due to force majeure at BTNS KC Poor; (12) Influence level profitability And liquidity to adequacy capital in BTNS KC Diponegoro Surabaya; (13) Influence of Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Loan to Value, inflation, exchange rates, mortgage financing, and interest rates on Non Performing Loan/NPL at BTN KC Padang; (14) Influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, amount of credit disbursement, financial ratios and environmental ratios to income/profit in BTN; (15) The influence of credit distribution, other funds, and income on changes capital in BTN; (16) Influence Non Performing Loans/NPLs to Loans to Deposits Ratio/LDR, Home Collateral Credit/KAR at BTN; (17) Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR to well-being public in BTN KC Denpasar; (18) Influence person organization fit and workplace spirituality on turnover intention at BTN; (19) Influence of resources tangible to performance marketing in BTN KC Baubau; (20) Influence Fund Party Third/DPK to Net Profit Margin/NPM at BTN; (21) Effect of Earning Per Share and BI-7 Day Reverse Repos Rate to price share in BTN; (22) Influence E-Service Quality and E-Trust towards E-Satisfaction at BTN KC Bangkalan; (23) Implementation of Total Quality Management at BTNS KC Malang; (24) Application of Notary in The Transition of Receivables at CESSIE) on Non-Load Loans at BTN; (25) Forecasting profitability ratios using method trend quadratic in BTNS; (26) Role And function in well-being public; (27) Implementation of OJK regulation no. 48 of 2020; (28) Calculation of depreciation on fixed assets on Income Tax/PPH at BTN KC Manado; (29) Measurement of health level company with method Integrated Performance Measurements Systems, RBBR And RGEC in BTN, BTNS; (30) Measurement performance employee with algorithm Fuzzy Tsukamoto on division Customers Collection & Remedial Division/CCRD; (31) Measurement potency bankruptcy/financial distress using the Altman Z-Score model; (32) Comparison price share before And after apply E-Blink; (33) Control internal receivables business at BTN KC Manado; (34) Potential retail funds for customers using the Decision method Tree and Naïve Bayes based Optimize Selection at BTN KC Season City; (35) Procedures Debtor/SID Information System work at BTN KCP Cimanggu; (36) BI Checking work procedures in BTN KCP Cimanggu; (37) Ratio liquidity, solvency, And profitability in BTN; (38) System information on filing savings documents at BTNS KC Pekanbaru; (39) Information systems accountancy to reception cash in BTN KC Medan; (40) Source And use capital work at BTN KC Manado; (41) External funding sources from Cost of Capital at BTN; (42) Strategy development units business priority in BTN; (43) Valuation acquisition BTN; And (44) Value Ti use method Partial Adjustments Valuation with Static Speed of Adjustments.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

first, based on mapping the distribution of journal publications around State Savings Bank (BTN) Sharia and Conventional during the period 2003 to 2023 which originating from the accredited national journal Sinta, there are 395 published journal articles. Second, based on research topic mapping using VOSviewer bibliometric studies, results network visualization around the divided EPS ratio in Sharia and Conventional Banking become 15 cluster And 97 items topic. Cluster 1 consists from 13 topic, cluster 2 consists from 9 topic, cluster 3 consists from 9 topic, cluster 4 consists from 9 topics, cluster 5 consists from 8 topic, cluster 6 consists from 8 topic, cluster 7 consists 6 topic, cluster 8 consists from 6 topic, cluster 9 consists from 6 topic, cluster 10 consists from 4 topic, cluster 11 consists Draï 4 topic, cluster 12 consists of 4 topic, cluster 13 consists of 4 topics, cluster 14 consists of 4 topics, and cluster 15 consists of 3 topics. Third, based on mapping topic study use studies Library Researchs, there is 9 topics related to Sharia and Conventional Sharia Savings Banks (BTN), namely: (1) Factors that influence BTN's financial performance; (2) Factors that influence performance employee BTN; (3) Factors Which influence loyalty customers transaction in BTN; (4) Product BTN; (5) Financing Credit Ownership House/KPRat BTN; (6) Factors influencing the granting of credit to BTN; (7) Factors- factors that influence customers to take credit at BTN; (8) Comparison of BTN performance with bank other; And (9) Problem others who happen on BTN.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and

- Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW*. *Kompetensi (Competence: Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN*

KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan*

- Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18.
<https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research).*
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>